

New combinations in *Dicliptera* (Acanthaceae)

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Abstract: Nine new combinations and one new name are proposed here under the genus *Dicliptera* Juss. Additionally, lectotypes are designated for the names *Peristrophe pantjarensis* var. *taroemensis* Hochr., *P. yunnanensis* W.W.Sm. and *Psiloesthes elongata* Benoist.

Keywords: Australia, Borneo, China, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Indonesia, *Peristrophe*, *Psiloesthes*, Saudi Arabia, Vietnam and Yemen

Introduction

The genus *Dicliptera* Juss. is represented by about 235 species, distributed in the tropics and subtropics and extending to central and south USA (Singh, 2023; Manzitto-Tripp et al., 2022). Presently, *Peristrophe* Nees and *Psiloesthes* Benoist are synonymous to the genus *Dicliptera* (Manzitto-Tripp et al., 2022). Therefore, nine validly published taxa in *Peristrophe* and one from *Psiloesthes* are transferred here to the genus *Dicliptera*. Lectotypes for the names *Peristrophe pantjarensis* var. *taroemensis* Hochr., *P. yunnanensis* W.W.Sm. and *Psiloesthes elongata* Benoist are designated here in accordance with the guidelines and recommendations of Article 9 of the Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018).

Nomenclature

Dicliptera brassii (R.M.Barker) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Peristrophe brassii* R.M.Barker, J. Adelaide Bot. Gard. 9: 192. 1986.

Holotype: Australia, Queensland, Kennedy Road, Mount Tozer, August 1965, C.H. Gittins 1076 (BRI-AQ0006303!).

Distribution: Endemic to Australia (Queensland).

Dicliptera elongata (Benoist) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Psiloesthes elongata* Benoist, Notul. Syst. (Paris) 5: 113. 1936.

Lectotype (designated here): Vietnam, Tonkin, route from Than moi to Van linh, 11 December 1902, *D. Bois 174* (P04561525!, Figure 1); isolectotypes P04561523!, P04561524!.

Distribution: Endemic to Vietnam.

Notes: Benoist's types are known to be held at P and PC. Three specimens were traced for the name *Psiloesthes elongata* Benoist at P (P04561523, P04561524 and P04561525). Among these, the better-preserved specimen P04561525, is designated here as the lectotype as it agrees well with the protologue.

Dicliptera hemsleyi R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Dicliptera crinita* var. *floribunda* Hemsl., J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 26: 248. 1890. *Peristrophe floribunda* (Hemsl.) C.Y.Wu & H.S.Lo, Fl. Hainan. 3: 595. 1974.

Holotype: China, Hainan, 10 miles East of Hoihow, 1889, *A. Henry 8200* (K000884395!, Figure 2).

Distribution: Endemic to China (Fujian, Guangdong, Guizhou, Hainan, Hunan, Sichuan and Yunnan).

Etymology: Named after William Botting Hemsley (1843–1924), British Botanist.

Notes: The species epithet *floribunda* is preoccupied in the genus *Dicliptera* Juss. (*D. floribunda* Eastw., Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts 44: 607. 1909), therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Dicliptera monosemaeophora (Bremek.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Peristrophe monosemaeophora* Bremek., Blumea 10: 165. 1960.

Holotype: Borneo, Sarawak, Bah on the upper Rejang River, 17 August 1954, *W.M.A. Brooke 9043* (L); isotypes BM000950087! (Figure 3), G00236407! (Figure 4).

Distribution: Endemic to Borneo.

Dicliptera pantjarensis (Hochr.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Peristrophe pantjarensis* Hochr., Candollea 5: 235. 1934.

Holotype: Indonesia, Java, Goenoeng Pantjar, East of Buitenzorg (Bogor), 800 m, 17 September 1904, *B.P.G. Hochreutiner 1823* (G, not traceable).

Distribution: Endemic to Java (Indonesia).

Figure 1: Lectotype of *Psiloesthes elongata* Benoist (P04561525, © Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris)

Figure 2: Holotype of *Dicliptera crinita* var. *floribunda* Hemsli. (K000884395, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Figure 3: Isotype of *Peristrophe monosemaeophora* Bremek. (BM000950087, © The Natural History Museum, London)

Figure 4: Isotype of *Peristrophe monosemaeophora* Bremek. (G00236407, © Conservatoire et Jardin botaniques de la Ville de Genève)

Figure 5: Lectotype of *Peristrophe pantjarensis* var. *taroemensis* Hochr. (Z00000115, © Herbarium der Universität Zürich)

Figure 6: Lectotype of *Peristrophe yunnanensis* W.W.Sm. (E00706902, © Herbarium of Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh)

Dicliptera strigosa (C.Y.Wu & H.S.Lo) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Peristrophe strigosa* C.Y.Wu & H.S.Lo, Fl. Hainan. 3: 596. 1974.

Holotype: China, Hainan, Dongfang, S.H. Chun 11496 (SCBI).

Distribution: Endemic to China (Hainan).

Dicliptera taroemensis (Hochr.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Peristrophe pantjarensis* var. *taroemensis* Hochr., Candollea 5: 235. 1934. *Peristrophe taroemensis* (Hochr.) Bremek., Verh. Kon. Ned. Akad. Wetensch., Afd. Natuurk., Sect. 2., 45(2): 32. 1948.

Lectotype (designated here): Java, Preanger, Ravine of Tji Taroem waterfall, 450 m, 30 July 1904, B.P.G. Hochreutiner 1651 (Z000000115!, Figure 5).

Distribution: Endemic to Java (Indonesia).

Notes: Hochreutiner's types are known to be housed at G. However, only a single herbarium sheet of *Peristrophe pantjarensis* var. *taroemensis* Hochr. is currently extant at Z (Z000000115), and it is therefore designated here as the lectotype.

Dicliptera teklei (Ensermu) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Peristrophe teklei* Ensermu, Kew Bull. 58(3): 704. 2003.

Holotype: Eritrea, about 9 km on Massawa road from Asmara, after Sheghrini, 2300 m, 15°20' N, 39°00' E, 21 October 1984, S. Edwards & G.E. Tewoldeberhan 3553 (ETH000000168!).

Distribution: Eritrea, Ethiopia, Saudi Arabia and Yemen.

Dicliptera tianmuensis (H.S.Lo) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Peristrophe tianmuensis* H.S.Lo, Bull. Bot. Res., Harbin 8(1): 4. 1988.

Holotype: China, Zhejiang, Tian-mu-shan, 11 September 1956, H.Q. Zhu 340 (SCBI).

Distribution: Endemic to China (Zhejiang).

Dicliptera yunnanensis (W.W.Sm.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Peristrophe yunnanensis* W.W.Sm., Notes Roy. Bot. Gard. Edinburgh 10: 187. 1918.

Lectotype (designated here): China, Yunnan, Yangpi Valley, 25°40' N, 5000 ft, April 1914, G. Forrest 12279 (E00706902!, Figure 6); isoelectotype K000884389!.

Distribution: Endemic to China (Sichuan and Yunnan).

Notes: Two syntype specimens are extant for the name *Peristrophe yunnanensis* W.W.Sm.

(E00706902 and K000884389). Of these, the best one E00706902 is designated here as the lectotype.

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